

HJRS Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities \(HEC-Recognized for 2022-2023\)](#)

Edition Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3\(3\) July-September 2023](#)

License: [Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International License](#)

Link of the Paper: <https://jar.bwo.org.pk/index.php/jarh/article/view/292>

CRITICAL REVIEW OF EIGHT EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON WASH-BACK IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TESTING

Author 1:	ABDUL RASHEED SOOMRO , Lecturer in English at IELL, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Pakistan, soomrorasheed4u@gmail.com
Co-Author 2:	ALI SIDDIQUI , (PhD Scholar) at Institute of English Language and Literature, same above Email: scorpion_king2893@outlook.com
Corresponding Co-Author 3:	SYED HYDER RAZA SHAH , Department of English at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Sanghar Campus, Pakistan, syedhyderaza_sng@sbbusba.edu.pk

Paper Information

Citation of the paper:

(APA) Soomro. Abdul Rasheed, Siddiqui. Ali and Shah, Syed Hyder Raza, (2023). Critical Review of Eight Experimental Studies on wash-Back in English Language Testing. In Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3(3), 01–11.

Subject Areas:

- 1 English Language
- 2 Humanities

Timeline of the Paper:

Received on: 29-05-2023
Reviews Completed on: 15-09-2023
Accepted on: 20-09-2023
Online on: 22-09-2023

License:

[Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International License](#)

Recognized:

Published by:

Abstract

The Wash-back has a significant area of English Language Assessment Research (ELAR), which has succeeded in inviting considerable heed of the researchers over the years. Some substantial experimental studies relating to washback in English language testing have been conducted globally. This study aims to review and evaluate the eight most recent experimental or empirical research projects carried out on washback in English linguistic education (ELE), which have been downloaded and collected through internet surfing. Based on the review of eight research articles, this current study has been conducted to determine the theoretical foundations of impacts of tests, examinations, assessments, and evaluation in English language education as well as testing besides demonstrating the research findings. Results showed that the washback of high-risk investigations or tests had positive, negative, and mixed impacts and effects depending on the backgrounds and language of students' extents. The positive washback affects the instructors, teaching practices, materials, methodologies, contents, and language beginner approaches, while the inverse or negative washback happens after the attention is diverted from the erudition process of English to test conducting approaches. After reviewing eight research projects, the findings stated that washback plays a crucial role in English language testing. In some cases, it is positive; in others, it has shown a negative stance. Therefore, it is difficult to state that all English tests positively impact test takers.

Keywords: English, Experimental, Washback, learner strategies, review, Testing, high risks

Introduction

The standard of psychological and academic tests is a group of five pieces of evidence that might be useful in evaluating high-stakes examinations, which include (a) exam content, (b) response procedures, (c) internal structure, (d) relations to other variables (e) significances of the exam. The examinations are normally taken with the anticipation that certain advantages would be comprehended from the envisioned usage of the marks. A fundamental purpose of validation is to indicate whether these specific benefits are understood. Hughes (1993) establishes that backwash is the effective of examinations upon both learning and teaching. However, Messick (1996) recommends that washback is the extent to which the overview and usage of an exam impact linguistic instructors. The learners tend to either promote or impede the learning of language. Swain (1985) stated that it is recurrently realized that instructors would impart knowledge towards an exam, whether they are cognizant of the content and the design of an examination the teachers would be teaching their pupils. An item of testing tails wagging the edification dog (Fullilove, 1992). Since the inception of the washback effect in 1993, the concept of the impact of testing particularly high-stakes assessment, was gained after the research project carried out by (Alderson & Wall, 1993) when their research work was published in a leading journal titled, "Does washback exist?" Earlier, Hughes (1989) termed this term as backwash and established that the impact of testing and assessments, particularly high-stakes tests, was specified for language learning and teaching and learning to ensure learning and teaching after examinations. Later, Alderson & Wall (1993) termed the term 'washback'. Earlier, Popham (1987) called the term a measurement-driven structure, and Frederiksen & Collins (1989) indicated it as systematic validity. Thus, Madaus (1988) & Smith (1991) termed the

same term as curriculum alignment. According to Baker (1991) and Wall (1997), washback or backwash refers to the term 'impact' while Messick (1989, 1996) supposed it as consequential validity.

1.1. Problem Statement

According to Madaus (1988), the testing is not the formally identified curriculum, but it is progressively what the things are imparted, in what way the things are taught or educated, and what are the things that are learned in addition to that by what means the things are learned.

1.2. Aim of Study

The current study explores eight studies from the last ten years, i.e., 2010-2020) regarding washback to scrutinize whether these studies validate this situation. The term 'washback' speaks of the effect of test and assessment practices on the procedure of schooling and learning.

1.3. Research Objective

To review and evaluate the impact of the eight most recent experimental research projects carried out on washback in English Linguistic Education (ELE).

1.4. Research Question

What is the impact of the eight most recent experimental research projects on washback in English linguistic education (ELE)?

1.5. Significance of Study

Fundamentals and principles for comprehending and virtually putting on results to analysis in testing effect depend on elucidating, clarifying, and investigating the idea of washback. The objective of the current review is to play that role. This review would assist further in comprehending the complication and the nature of washback that could enable instructors, assessment developers, teachers, curriculum or syllabus experts and other participants to manage such examinations that generate a constructive impact.

2. Literature Review

Many researchers defined the term "washback" in their own way, and some of

the researchers have been positioned in the consortium of test impact, washback and backwash that are given below:

- (1) Test Impact, (2) Backwash, and (3) Washback

2.1. Test Impact

According to scholars, assessments possess across-the-board effects in the academic domain than in the English language classroom. In this regard, [Bachman & Palmer \(1996\)](#) employed the word 'impact', referring to impacts in examinations display characters, which include instructors and learners or tests bring academic reforms, ameliorating the educational system by putting effects on the social order altogether. [Wall \(1997\)](#) possessed an identical outlook by uttering that "test impact brings up some impacts which an examination might have upon the persons, strategies or performances in the classroom, the social order, the academic institutions, and in the school at large". [McNamara \(2004\)](#) affirmed that tests could have impacts outside the classroom as well. He established that "the broader influence of tests or examinations on the public at large including the basic educational institutions is stated by way of test impact". However, [Andrews \(2004\)](#) employed the impact of tests to refer to the impacts of assessments, tests or examinations on the educational system, different stakeholders relating to education activities and the teaching and learning process.

2.2. BackWash

[Hughes \(1989\)](#) defines backwash specifically by saying that it is all about the influence and impact of assessment on learning and teaching. According to [Spolsky \(1994\)](#), backwash is a word that engages with the unpredicted side-effects of examination but not to the envisioned influences at the time when the key objective of the assessment becomes to regulate the syllabi or courses. According to [Biggs \(1995\)](#), backwash means "assessment regulates the

curriculum along with instructors' training and learners' erudition approaches.

2.3. Washback

[Pearson \(1988\)](#) defines washback as how community testing affects the behaviors, performances, attitudes, conducts, and inspirations of instructors, students, and their blood relations. Because the testing always follows a course or syllabus is completed. This effect is experienced functioning in a regressive track; therefore, the term is called 'washback'. Much like the study of [Hughes \(1989\)](#) regarding washback, [Bailey \(1996\)](#) established it to be the influence and impact of assessment on the process and procedure of learning and teaching. Another researcher, [Messick \(1996\)](#), defined the term washback in quite a similar way. The researcher said that the degree or amount to which the overview summary and usage of an examination affect linguistics and instructors equally; otherwise, they will not do the same, which endorses or prevents English language learning. [Alderson & Wall \(1993\)](#) defined the word [washback] as a phenomenon or wonder that forces instructors and students to do several things/hardworking on account of the examination. [Shohamy et al. \(1996\)](#) described this word of English [washback] similarly by uttering it as the link between assessment and erudition. According to [Cheng \(2005\)](#), washback designates the intentional and the unintentional direction and task for syllabus alteration (change of curriculum) upon the characteristics to teach and learn through a modification of community testing.

2.4. Theoretical Framework

The pioneer researchers [Alderson & Wall \(1993\)](#) established around fifteen (15) wash-back suggestions along with recommendations which are about the effects that what is impacted: the number of instructors or students influenced by an assessment, attitudes, behaviors, content, approaches, teaching, sequence, strategies, rate, learning, level, depth and degree. All these fifteen (15) hypotheses comprise that

an examination would affect (i) what is erudition of students, (ii) what the instructors impart to the learners, (iii) what are the parameters by which the students learn, (iv) what the parameters of teaching by the instructors (v) learning, (vi) the height or extent of learning, (vii) teaching, (viii) the order or sequence and level of imparting edification to students, (ix) the gravity and grade (depth and degree) of teaching, (x) the gravity and grade of learning, (xi) Testing possesses washback effects only for certain English language learners as well as certain instructors, (xii) Examination which does not possess any significant outcomes has no any washback, (xiii) attitudes and orientation towards the technique and content of teaching as well as learning, (xiv) Assessment possesses washback on instructors and students, and (xv) testing has washback upon the instructors and students. During a study of washback, the focus might be placed upon the students, instructors, publishers, and material developers (participants), partakers' activities towards erudition (process), and the quality of erudition or learning and that what is learned (products) as recommended by Hughes (1993) in his trichotomy model and cited well by another researcher Bailey (1996). Consequently, Saville (2009) introduced and presented the idea of (the 3Ps), which refers to washback's three leading characteristics: products, participants, and processes. Figure 1, given below, can be seen for further details in this regard.

Figure 1: Baily's (1996) Fundamental Model of Washback

Looking at the opposite aspect, washback is hypothesized and abstracted by a researcher, Watanabe (2004), about dimensions including value, rate, length, measurement, specificity, amount, intentionality, force, intensity, and strength of the washback, characteristics of teaching and learning procedure which might be affected and impacted by the assessment, and the determinants intervening the washback process being germinated and developed which include macro-context determinants, esteem determinants, personal determinants and assessment determinants. To the kinds that are concerned, the two important kinds of washback might have been noticed. These both include positive and negative washback. As stated by Alderson & Wall (1993), the positive washback mentions the assessments or testing that will constructively influence this entire procedure and process of schooling and erudition. Taylor (2005) proved that "the assessment methods promote and encourage 'sound' teaching practices or schooling performances". Both the instructors and learners adopted an optimistic approach or orientation to assessment with the start of working willingly to achieve the aim.

In contrast, negative washback takes place when assessment format and content depend upon a thin representation or description of linguistic proficiency, and it restricts teaching and learning situations. According to Brown (2004), as cited in Alderson and Wall (1993), this mentions the unattractive or negative effect on an assessment of teaching and learning that means "a weak assessment wherein the extents or goings-on which an instructor or a learner does not want to demonstrate or hit the books and an inconsistency or divergence between the content which include the substantial/capabilities being imparted, and

the assessment. It gets the shape of a 'negative washback' once there is an inconsistency or disagreement between the assessment or the content, including things/capabilities being imparted to the learners and the construct definition (hypothesis description).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The current study is review-based research that depends on secondary data. The cutting-edge literature or works on washback research projects have been reviewed and investigated from 2010 to 2020.

3.2. Data Instrument

The research papers were gathered with the help of the Google search engine. The studies were downloaded from the websites of different universities, peer-reviewed online research journals, Research Gate, Science Direct, Google Scholar and ERIC by searching the keywords like assessment, examinations, testing, analysis, washback studies, and reliability, validity & washback etcetera. Data, statistics, facts and figures retrieved, recovered, and extracted from different secondary sources have been properly recognized and admitted accordingly.

4. Main Findings from Eight Experimental Studies

In the following study, eight experiential research projects to washback towards teaching of language were reviewed, studied, and investigated. These eight empirical studies have been conducted across the globe during the last 10 years from 2010 to 2020. The most important conclusions and results of the said research have been examined and assessed as following:

4.1. Cholis and Rizqi (2019) - Admission Test at institutions of higher education (ATIHE) in Indonesia

In conclusion, a smaller emphasis was given to reading conception, comprehension, or ability. The research findings described a 'positive washback'; subsequently, the

instructors skilled the learners hinged upon curriculum or courses apart from ATIHE design. As a result, the research of [Cholis & Rizqi \(2019\)](#) disclosed that examination had never brought any 'negative backwash' because the pedagogy had never totally depended on (pre-entrance test) designs, patterns, and strategies with contents. In contrast, the respondent instructors in the majority participated in the prevailing study and did not expect to undertake innovative teaching approaches and use factual tasks that were instances of 'negative washback'. Simultaneously, reviewing certain prevailing materials and things, facing new trials and challenges in teaching, organizing fresh goals and purposes of teaching, and organizing further test practices and actions for the ATIHE exam were specimens of what is called "training to the pre-entrance test". Test practices were assessed as the undesirable impacts (or negative effects) of entry tests in this prevailing study. On the other hand, the conclusion of this study further established that the desirable impacts (or positive effects) of the pre-entry test/ assessment outweighed and balanced the undesirable impacts.

4.2. Khoshsima, Saed, and Mousaei (2018) - Impact on Teach through Test-taking Approaches concerning (Reading) Section at IELTS in Iran

The following research tried to evaluate the effects of demonstrating reading-based assessment approaches for IELTS aspirants at coaching academies in Iran. [Khoshsima, Saed & Mousaei \(2018\)](#) conducted their study on 40 participants through an empirical research design wherein the investigational group consisted of 20 participants who were given exam-taking guidelines, while another control group comprised another 20 participants who were given traditional or general guidelines. Earlier, they [researchers] tested the partakers' competence level (homogeneity) to jump to a conclusion. Subsequently, during the schooling period/

class, the scholars conducted the reading examination from the forty contestants and recorded the outcomes. Therefore, results revealed that the mean score for those partakers in an empirical group, given taking of test guidelines to reading ability that have been higher to those participants included in (control) group, imparted language education with a general approach. Therefore, in their research, [Khoshsima, Saed & and Mousaei \(2018\)](#) established that the examination-taking approaches of teaching positively impacted IELTS learners' performance in Iran upon the reading part of the test. According to the researchers, they had taken the acuity from the participants of the empirical group about teaching-related exam-taking approaches, and the results showed an identical response: 'positive orientations'. This study ended with the recommendations that teaching approaches are fruitful for the exam conductors (test-takers) upon an unambiguous point within the IELTS test process.

4.3. Munoz (2017) – Test Scale Approaches (TSA) in Chile

A researcher in [Chile & and Munoz \(2017\)](#), conducted a study on the students' approaches toward assessment or tests. This research was conducted in the frame of empirical research design wherein twenty-five participants were included in the empirical group while twenty-seven partakers were made a part of the control group. Again, he [the researcher] continuously imparted the required English language education to the participants of the divided groups for 4 hours per week for 16 weeks. He kept on teaching the participants of the control group through the general practice by assigning them test outcomes in the form of grades while he started teaching the candidates of the empirical group through the methods of washback by which the researcher categorized the exams and wrote down quizzes, assigned them to the participants and talked over the responses.

The results revealed that participants for the empirical group possessed a good attitude and orientation towards exams about in what way these tests or exams lent a hand to them to mug up the contents, improve test-taking approaches, for instance, time management abilities, augment confidence or self-possession as well as motivation and inspiration. This research ended with suggestions to employ washback procedures and designate the progress and perfection of plaintiffs' orientation, attitude, and motivation toward testing and appraisal.

4.4. Khodabakhsh, Zard, & Ali (2017) - Mock Tests Impacts (MTI) on IELTS Entrants in Iran

The researchers tried to observe and discover if the mock tests of IELTS or a preparatory exam can benefit the candidates who are aspirants in clearing the IELTS test with sound scores. The researchers attempted to experience the impact of IELTS preparatory syllabi and in what way the outcome of the IELTS courses will be able to help the material designers, course inventors, and syllabus developers exclude or include such substances in the curriculum. Like the binary erstwhile studied research projects, this prevailing research had also been done in empirical design wherein twenty-five partakers were included in the first group while another twenty-six participants were pun in the second group. The data was collected from their annotations and remarks submitted by the respondents who hailed from the intermediate and unconventional (advanced) levels. These participants hitherto had not partaken in any course of IELTS. So, the first group participants were given mock tests for their session, and the outcomes were transmitted to partakers before the next expected session. In contrast, participants of the second group were taught conventional empirical instructions, such as responding to some queries, separating tasks into subdivisions, and elucidating the method. The researchers held ten periods

with a short span of three months, then matched post-exam scores or marks to partakers of the first and second groups. Conclusions of this research discovered that an important modification was found between the post-exam marks of both groups, whereas the second group overtook and outpaced the first group. However, this study found that employing exam-taking approaches was more efficient than teaching curriculum content regarding high-stakes examinations, such as IELTS. Hence, this study supported the utilization of mock examinations in the IELTS preparing syllabus on account of positive washback in the Islamic Republic of Iran.

4.5. Barnes (2016) – Wash-back Observed in TOEFL (Vietnam)

Barnes (2016) studied the impacts of TOEFL on schooling substances and teaching pedagogy/ education. He singled out two leading coaching academies working for English language learning in Vietnam. These academies offered only one program, which was TOEFL tuition classes. The researcher gathered the required data from the teaching materials available in these academies in addition to classroom annotations and elucidations. However, he established instructors' extra reliance upon the iBT book designed and published for TOEFL candidates besides the presence of marketable materials and resources. He observed that the provisions in bulk gathered from the classroom annotations had not been generated by the instructors, but these observations had come straight from the textbooks taught in the classroom. Consequently, the teaching procedures were not impacted or affected considerably because of their dependence upon iBT course book materials or resources concerning TOEFL. In addition, the experienced tasks in abundance anticipated learners to answer the queries separately. The researcher witnessed that the communications within classroom jurisdiction were present from the

learners to learners, learners to their instructors, and vice versa. Thus, the instances of the learners to their counterparts or communication in the classroom are contained within verbal demonstrations and deliberations within the classroom. This research established that coaching goes on rather than teaching activities grabbed supplementary time within the classroom than learners' activities. So, the results of this research recommended that the programs of iBT tuition or coaching of TOEFL stressed the need to develop examination abilities, but these abilities are optional for learning or becoming skilled in English language or verbal communication. Therefore, this research established the negative effects of the iBT examination of TOEFL on teaching contents and training practices.

Studies	Barnes (2016)	Munoz (2017)	Khodabakhshzadeh, Zardkanto, and Alipour (2017)	Khoshsima, Saad and Mousael (2018)	Cholis (2019)
Exams Studied	TOEFL iBT in Vietnam	Attitude towards Test Scale (ATS) in Chile	Mock tests in IELTS preparation courses in Iran	Test-taking strategies on reading section of academic IELTS in Iran	Pre-En indom Univer
Purposes	To examine about the washback impacts of stakes (high) English language aptitude examination, TOEFL with iBT within Vietnam.	To improve learners' attitudes towards tests	To explore whether, the Mock-IELTS exam have effect to candidates of IELTS. It is overall score in IELTS Exam	To explore and impact to read and teach. It take test for strategies on candidates of IELTS. The performance reading in section of IELTS.	To did Wash- influer stakes exami upon i orient; teachi appro simple
Methodology	Observational data were collected	(Action research- mixed) method design, interview and the questionnaire	(Experimental) design that divides participants within two groups and compare (post-test scores)	Experimental design experimental (group). It received taking of instructions and (control) group received general instructions	Survey and questi
Collected Evidence	The materials were dependent on TOEFL iBT test books. The teaching pedagogies did not change due to over dependence	Empirical group recorded greater than that of the (control) group. Empirical group have presented the positive Attitudes within the tests	Group practiced through Mock-test. It out-performed Groups. It did not have for the mock-test	The score of (experimental) group than (general) group. The participants had optimistic attitude	The ps teache optimi attitude They p few questi in metho teachi

Table 1: Five Research Projects of Washback

4.6. Aftab, Qureshi, and William (2015) - English Testing Strategies (ETS) at Intermediate Level in Pakistan

In their research, Aftab, Qureshi, and William (2015) examined and inspected the scope, background, and environment of the 'washback influence' concerning English testing strategies at the intermediate or FA/ FSc level at the colleges in Pakistan that candidates' admission in the universities. This research adopted a qualitative data-gathering technique employing interviews to seek the opinions of the instructors and their

pupils. However, the replying college pupils called for the preparation of testing-related undertakings. They hinged upon providing notes in bulk rather than preparation course books and guides available in the market. According to this study, the college students' inclination towards learning the responses to various selected questions by heart for the intended examinations recommended and considered English as a simple form of the subject. It passed the annual examination well not have been treated as an international language to be learned fully and spoken accordingly.

Concurrently, the instructors greatly and solely hinged upon practicing testing linked responsibilities. Consequently, this research discovered that the exams possessed a 'negative washback' upon the content, teaching approach, and erudition as several pupils' desires regarding English language learning were ignored during English-related testing at the intermediate English across Pakistan.

4.7. Watanabe (2014) - Centre Exam for Entry (CEE) to Varsities in Japan

Watanabe (2014) researched the domestic central pre-entrance test from the students to seek enrolment at different universities in Japan, which is said to be a feat test conducted annually at various locations across the country. This center test processes candidates' feat of the previous year's higher secondary stage. The researcher tried to find the central examination's effect, authentication, and validation. Central testing decides candidates' entry into state-run public and privately run higher education institutions. It also tries to ameliorate the process of teaching and learning to help the candidates improve their talkative abilities. The exam contains two important sections, which include listening and writing elements. The National Centre for University Entrance Test (NCUET) creates and develops this test. According to Watanabe (2014), the pre-entrance test was reasonable and judicious in

measuring the candidates, and it delivered an effective dimension of learners' capability to be enrolled at higher education institutions. In addition, this research investigated the exam marks or scores achieved by the candidates. It also established that the candidates got hold of the extent of mandatory feat and the marks or scores anticipated the applicant's triumph at the national universities of Japan. Moreover, the examination affected the upgrading of 'test preparation substances' at the academies that cope with pre-college-extent tutoring. The researcher lastly established that the examination possessed a 'positive washback' upon the students and coaching-related materials and resources.

4.8. Kirkpatrick (2013) - Washback Impact of the English Testing Method (ETM) in Bhutan

In his research, Kirkpatrick (2013) scrutinized the washback impact of the English testing Method (ETM) allied with the fresh syllabus of higher secondary schools in Bhutan. The curriculum was revised before the commencement of the academic year 2006. So, the data for this study was gathered from fifty-six instructors of English as a foreign language hailing from the higher secondary schools using survey responses. This research recommended that the innovative syllabus and testing method carried/ possessed both negative and positive wash-back. So, the positive wash-back impacts brought into being in the research were instructors' readiness (willingness) to accept novel methodologies to coaching, diagnostic reaction alongside the score awarded to the students by the instructors, utilization of instruments, descriptions (rubrics), and worksheet mockups for testing. In this study, the negative washback happened because of the misalliance among curriculum substances and time apportionment, the mammoth amount of work on learners and lecturers, and the predisposition of score increase. Moreover,

the determinants such as shortage of instructors' preparation, paucity of syllabus provisions, jam-packed classrooms, and over-emphasis upon the collective test, headed towards the negative effects. So, this research suggested keeping equilibrium or balance in the middle of formative as well as summative testing. The researcher further revealed that the new testing method introduced certain alterations, modifications, and upgrading of coaching and erudition at higher secondary schools in the country like Bhutan, nevertheless, the same did not meet the workstation, educational, and growth needs and desires of modern Bhutan. Furthermore, the researcher mentioned that several instructors were not able to act upon the new testing method; however, they could evaluate the learners with appropriate assistance.

to the instructional actions of teachers whether and in what way, the parents can be included in their progenies' erudition practices and actions, and similarly significant, that what sorts of students having which educational/ academic and socio-cultural background are located therein. By taking these steps, the instructors could certainly augment their ability, capacity, and skills to bring about 'positive washback influences'.

5. Discussion

This review research covered the experimental studies on 'washback impacts' in republics such as Pakistan, Bhutan, Chile, Vietnam, Iran, Indonesia, and Japan. The research projects, eight in total, consisted of high-stakes tests, including pre-entry tests to seek admission to higher education institutions (universities), domestic tests, TOEFL, IELTS, and others. So, the revised research projects were pursued carefully to recognize and categorize washback's scope, environment, and nature, its impacts on teaching approaches, instructors' and students' orientations, attitudes, outlooks, and test-taking approaches. The approaches of the research projects eight in number surveyed were action research, qualitative research, survey design, and empirical research design, wherein the statistics were gathered with the assistance of classroom observations, interviews of students and teachers, and a questionnaire. The proof gathered from the reviewed eight research projects discovered the positive orientations, attitudes, and motivations of the instructors' students' healthier competition in taking the examination. On the other hand, the proof was also destined to be negative when the learners gave the response for the examination, and the instructors imparted merely the skills and polished the talents of the students confirmed in the testing. Besides, the washback impacts were seldom mixed to be negative and positive. It occurred

Studies	Kirkpatrick (2013)	Watanabe (2014)	Aftab, Qureshi and William (2014)
Tests Studied	English Assessment System in Bhutan	Center Test for University Admissions (an achievement test) in Japan	Intermediate English Examination within Pakistan
Purposes	To inspect wash-back effect to assessment of English system	Explored the test validation and its effects on students' achievement	Discover scope, range and nature of the washback impact under the intermediate, FA or FSc English test in Pakistani context
Methodology	Questionnaire	qualitative research method exploratory analysis	Qualitative design interviews
Collected Evidence	Instructors' readiness to take new methods to teaching, diagnostic feedback, use of rubrics. Lack of teacher training, lack of curriculum materials, crowded classes, and overemphasis on summative assessment	Measured the skills that were supposed to be measured. Students developed communicational skills which were tested in the test	Students crammed answers. The teachers taught only the skills that were tested in the test
Conclusion	New curriculum or syllabus produced both negative and positive washback.	Central examination had positive washback	The test had negative washback on teaching-learning, content and teaching methodology

Table 2: Three Research Projects on Washback

The teachers can contribute towards policy making at the higher level in Pakistan. They can also contribute towards curriculum or syllabus, at which point tests are developed and advanced, whether in what way the instructors solve learners' erudition needs, desires, requirements, styles, and flairs, in what way the learners react or answer back

because of the alteration of students' heights and their backgrounds.

6. Recommendations: The instructors can acquire knowledge even from the available research projects written on washback and they must have the following three qualities:

1. The instructors/ teachers must be fully cognizant of the existence of washback.
2. They should comprehend the impacting determinants of washback.
3. They ought to increase their knowledge regarding academic concepts and philosophies concerning washback.

7. Conclusion

The research studies, eight in number, yielded numerous outcomes about washback. For example, it was noticed that washback could be clearer and more comprehensible instead of possessing a direct as well as a meek impact. Consequently, washback is considered extremely comprehensive, taking numerous variables apart from the examination. Again, certain determinants that influenced washback take account of instructor and learner elements such as personality, education, attitudes, orientations, beliefs, training, learning flair, experience, publishers, course book authors and textbook developers such as their analyses and clarification of testing needs, the standing of the topics to be conducted exam, communication between providers and users of the examination, materials & class environment, organization of activities in the schools & colleges, and the socio-political background wherein the examination is to be conducted, etcetera. Moreover, though the outer determinants like instructor or learner elements have been recognized, an inadequate study has been conducted to disclose how these work and network alongside an examination to produce the outcomes detected. Regarding pedagogical matters, the current reviewed study discloses that instructors play a significant role in producing negative or positive washback

impacts. Consequently, these should be an essential determinant of any experimental research on the 'washback'. Thus, they have dynamic characteristics in the pedagogical enactments of producing a 'positive washback' envisioned by exam designers' legislators and anticipated by the candidates and their close relatives.

References

- Aftab, Asma, Qureshi, S, William, I. (2015). *Investigating the washback effect of the Pakistani Intermediate English Examination*. International Journal of English and Literature, 5, no.7 (2014): 149-154.
- Alderson, J. C., & Wall, D. (1993). Does washback exist? *Applied linguistics*, 14(2), 115-129.
- Andrews, S. (2004). Washback and curriculum innovation. In *Washback in language testing* (pp. 59-72). Routledge.
- Bailey, M. (1996). *Language teacher supervision*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Bailey, M. (1996). *Working for washback: A review of the washback concept in language testing*. Language Testing, 13 (1996): 257.
- Barnes, M. (2016). *The Washback Effects of the TOEFL iBT in Vietnam*. Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 41, no.7: 158-174.
- Biggs, B. (1995). *Assumptions underlying new approaches to assessment*. Curriculum Forum, 4: 1.
- Brown, H. (2004). *Language assessment principles and classroom practices*. Longman: Pearson Education.
- Cheng, L. (1997). *The Washback Effect of Public Examination Change on Classroom Teaching*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong.
- Cheng, L. (2005). *Changing Language Teaching Through Language Testing: A Washback Study*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

- Cholis, H., & Faricha, R. (2019). *Senior High School English Teachers' Perceptions on a High-Stakes Test (SBMPTN): A Washback Study*. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 6, no. 3: 47-52. doi: 10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.6n.3p.47.
- Frederiksen, J. R., & Collins, A. (1989). *A Systems Approach to Educational Testing*. *Educational Researcher*, 18, no. 9: 27-32.
- Fullilove, J. (1992). The tail that wags Institute of Language in Education journal (9), 130-147.
- Hughes, A. (1989). *Testing for language teachers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hughes, A. (1993). Backwash and TOFEL 2000. Unpublished manuscript. University of Reading, 49.
- Khodabakhshzadeh, H., Reza, Z., & Iman, A. (2018). *The Effect of Mock Tests on Iranian EFL Learners' Test Scores*. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 5, no.3: 47-51.
- Khoshsima, H. Amin, S., & Fatemeh, M. (2018). *Exploring the Effect of Teaching Test-Taking Strategies on Intermediate Level Learners on Reading Section of Ielts; Learners' Attitude in Focus*. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 9, no.2: 4-9.
- Kirkpatrick, R (2013). *Washback Effects of the New English Assessment System on Secondary Schools in Bhutan*. *Language Testing in Asia*, 2, no.4: 5-32.
- Madaus, F. (1988). *The influence of testing on the curriculum*. In Tanner, L.N., editor, *Critical issues in the curriculum: eighty-seventh yearbook of the National Society for the Study of Education (Part 1)*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Messick, S. (1989) *Validity*. In R. L. Linn (Ed.), *Educational Measurement* (3rd ed.) New York: ACE and Macmillan:13-103.
- Messick, S. (1996). Validity and washback in language testing. *Language Testing* 13(3), 241-256.
- Munoz, R. (2017) *The Effect of Washback on EFL Learners' Attitudes toward Tests*. *Studies in English Language Teaching*, 5, no.3: 516-530.
- Pearson, I. (1988). *Tests as levers of change (or putting first things first)*. In D. Chamberlain & R. Baumgartner (Eds.), *ESP in the classroom: Practice and evaluation* ELT Documents #128, (pp.98-107), Modern English Publication in association with the British Council, London.
- Popham, W. (1987). *The Merits of Measurement-Driven Instruction*. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 68: 679-682.
- Saville, D. (2009). *Developing a Model for Investigating the Impact of Language Assessment with Educational Contexts by a Public Examination Provider*. Bedfordshire: University Bedfordshire.
- Shohamy, E., & Donitsa-Schmidt, I. (1996). *Test impact revisited: Washback effect over time*. *Language Testing* 13: 298.
- Smith, L. (1991). *Put to the test: The effects of external testing on teachers*. *Educational Researcher*, 20, no. 5: 8-11.
- Spolsky, B. (1994). *The examination of classroom backwash cycle: Some historical cases*, in Nunan, D, Berry, V and Berry, R. (Eds) *Bringing about change in language education*, University of Hong Kong, Dept. of Curriculum Studies, Hong Kong.
- Swain, M. (1985). Large scale communicative testing: A case study. In Y. P. Lee, A.C.V. Fok, R. Lord, and G. Low (Eds), *New direction in language testing* (pp, 35-46). Oxford Pargamon Press.
- Taylor, L. (2005). *Washback and impact*. *English Language Teaching Journal*, 59: 154-155.
- Wall, D. (1997). *Impact and washback in language testing*, In C. C. & D. Corson (Eds.), *Encyclopaedia of language and education, Language Testing and Assessment* 7: 291.
- Watanabe, Y. (2013). *The National Center Test for University Admissions*. *Language Testing*, 30, no.4: 565-573.